

Destroy Your Enemy Becoming Your Friend: Priam and the Amazons in the Trojan War

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INTRODUCTION

Achilles, one of the great heroes of Greek mythology associated with the Trojan War, makes the story of the confrontation between the Achaeans and the Trojans, including the episode involving Queen Penthesilea, the crucial epic event of antiquity.¹ Any self-respecting Greek mythical hero would have counted a victory over such mighty warriors among his exploits. Even considering only the number of known sources, this story is one of the most widespread, after the Ninth Labor and the Adventure of Theseus, albeit with significant omissions.²

The most important of these sources is Homer himself, the main narrator of these events, whose account does not mention Penthesilea. Nevertheless, he was aware of this tradition since he was the

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1 Arctinus of Miletus; cf. Proclus (*Chr.* 2; *Schol. Hom. Il.*, 24.804); Stesichorus (Tz. ad Lyc. 266); Lyc. (cf. Tz. ad Lyc. 266); Ps.-Apollod., *Ep.* 5.1; Verg., *Aen.* 1.488–93; Iust., *Epit.* 2.31–32; Str. 12.24; Ovid *AA.*, 2.741–46 and 3.1–5; Dictys Cretensis 3.15–16; Thrasyll. Mend., *FHG.* 3.503, 3; Paus. 1.16; Plin., *NH* 5.115; Q. S. 1.48–53, 559–62, 568–74, 724–29 and 800–9; Seru. Hon. 1.491; Ptol. Heph. 6 (cf. Phot., *Bibl.* 190); Sen., *Tro.* 236 ff.; Diodorus Siculus 2.46; Hyg., *Fab.* 163; Triph. (cf. Tz., *PH.* 209); Dares Phrygius 36.

2 Sánchez Sanz, *Ars Amazonica*, 25.

first to allude to these mythical figures in his work.³ Moreover, we can intuit an earlier origin for this episode since the first written reference corresponds to another contemporary poet, Arctinus of Miletus (8th century BC), who reappears shortly afterward in the works of Stesichorus (7th century BC). Nevertheless, there are no further mentions of him until the 3rd century BC, although his memory was present in the collective imaginary through numerous artistic works dated throughout antiquity and tradition.⁴

Homer himself was likely aware of this tradition since he mentions the Amazons twice in his verses in the *Iliad*, but the episode takes place chronologically after the death of Prince Hector, so he could not include it in this work, which only recounts the events of the Trojan War up to that point. However, Homer's account is important for placing the events that happened later in context – especially the ones concerning the Amazons, since the authors who mention the events of the Amazon queen were familiar with Homer's work and were obliged to try to explain Penthesilea's attitude and her relationship with Priam before recounting the battle that would lead to her losing her life to the greatest of the Achaean heroes. We will also analyze the few archaeological sources that offer us representations directly related to this episode to conduct a comparative analysis between both sources to know the different existing versions of these myths.

Homer has become the leading exponent of the Greek epic, but it would be inappropriate to regard him as its creator since he was undoubtedly well acquainted with other contemporary and earlier poems.⁵ However, this article does not intend to analyze the degree of originality or tradition of the Homeric poems in search of their sources since they represent only a minor part of the history of the Trojan War. In this respect, our interest differs from the neo-analytic methodology, although we accept many of its findings. We are interested in focusing on how many (or all) characters appearing in his poems were already well-known to his audience.⁶ This certainty could have originated in earlier poems and the oral tradition, which transmitted the mythical stories. For this reason, Homer did not need to explain who Batiea was; it

3 Hom., *Il.* 2.811–14.

4 Transmitted mainly by the female element in society; Buxton, *Imaginario*, 31; Veyne, *Creveron*, 80; Sanchez Sanz, *Deconstructing*, 11.

5 Burgess, *The tradition*, 2. Foley and Arft, *The Epic Cycle*, 94.

6 Sanchez Sanz, *Viral*, 12.

was not necessary because everyone knew her, and that is why we have considered it more appropriate to apply the methodology of intertextuality⁷ to the oral traditions related to the Amazon episode analyzed in this work.

ἔστι δέ τις προπάροιθε πόλιος αἰπεῖα κολώνη
 ἐν πεδίῳ ἀπάνευθε περιδρομος ἔνθα καὶ ἔνθα,
 τὴν ἦτοι ἄνδρες Βατίειαν κικλήσκουσιν,
 ἀθάνατοι δὲ τε σῆμα πολυσκάρθμοιο Μυρίνης·

Now there is before the city a steep mound afar out in the plain, with a clear space about it on this side and on that; this do men verily call Batieia, but the immortals call it the barrow of Myrine, light of step.

Hom., *Il.* 2.811–14

Our reference is to contextualized intertextual analyses of the information related to the appearance of the Amazons in Troy as part of the epic cycle, as opposed to the perhaps too superficial analysis proposed by authors such as Malcolm⁸ when he mentions a very different image of women in the *Aethiopsis* of Arctinus of Miletus and the *Iliad*. However, this is not the case since Homer neither denies the power of the Amazons nor avoids mentioning them (although he could have done so without any problem). This paper leaves aside the Unitarians of the nineteenth century and the Neoanalysts and Oralists of today, as it does not adhere faithfully to any of these schools of thought. However, it recognizes that all of them provide helpful methodological tools for analyzing the characters of the epic cycle. It is sometimes necessary to move away from dogmatism to apply a holistic approach to analyzing the available sources.⁹ In short, there was probably a rich and long oral tradition of poems about the Trojan War, from which the poems that now make up the epic cycle were later fixed in writing. What form this fixation took, who composed them, and how many different versions there were are still matters of debate.

7 Nagy, *Pindar's*, 70–79.

8 Malcolm, *The Greek*, 51.

9 Sanchez Sanz, *El corazón*, 12.

WRITTEN SOURCES

Most stories of the Amazons were well known in antiquity,¹⁰ but those relating the Trojan king Priam to the Amazons correspond to the famous episode of Penthesilea, who became his ally to confront the Achaeans and who perished at the gates of the city after a single battle with Achilles. Arctinus of Miletus recalled such events as early as the 8th century BC, becoming one of the first known authors whose texts reference the mythical Amazon universe.¹¹ However, he was not the only one.

At the same time, Homer, while referring to an epic dedicated to the narration of the Trojan War, concludes his contribution without mentioning Penthesilea. On the contrary, he gives us three passages showing that these traditions were much more numerous than we think and that their origin was lost even further back in time. He alludes to the myth of Bellerophon,¹² the existence of the Libyan Amazons, and the moment when a young Priam decided to take on the mighty Amazons.¹³

ἤδη καὶ Φρυγίην εἰσήλυθον ἀμπελόεσσαν,
 ἔνθα ἴδον πλείστους Φρύγας ἀνέρας αἰολοπῶλους,
 λαοὺς Ὀτρῆος καὶ Μυγδόνος ἀντιθέοιο,
 οἳ ῥα τότε ἔστρατώνοντο παρ' ὄχθας Σαγγαρίοιο·
 καὶ γὰρ ἐγὼν ἐπικούρος ἐὼν μετὰ τοῖσιν ἐλέχθην
 ἤματι τῷ, ὅτε τ' ἦλθον Ἀμαζόνες ἀντιάνειραι·

Ere now have I journeyed to the land of Phrygia, rich in vines, and there I saw in multitudes the Phrygian warriors, masters of glancing steeds, even the people of Otreus and godlike Mygdon, that were then encamped along the banks of Sangarius. For I, too, being their ally, was numbered among them on the day when the Amazons came, the peers of men.

Hom., *Il.* 3.184–89 (translation by A.T. Murray)

10 Sanchez Sanz, *Mujeres*, 146.

11 Procl., *Chr.* 2; *Schol. Hom. Il.* 24.804.

12 The hero faced the Amazons with the help of Pegasus; Sanchez Sanz, *Belerofonte*, 40.

13 Hom., *Il.* 3.184–89.

Homer does not devote many more verses to this section on the Trojan monarch than to the others, although the chronological moment in which the action takes place leaves no doubt that it took place long before the Achaeans presented themselves at the gates of Ilion. Unsurprisingly, one of the main problems it raises will have a direct impact on the credibility that many later authors gave to the Penthesilea episode since some found it impossible that this ruler would choose to ally herself with the Trojans when that monarch had long before acted as their enemy.¹⁴ Perhaps for the same reason, some of the sources that recount the battle between Penthesilea and Achilles had to explain this change of attitude on the part of the Amazons by claiming that it was due more to the need for expiation than for the good relations between the two Near Eastern peoples since it was not equally necessary to justify the interest of Priam, whom his enemies besieged after the death of Hector.

Homer says that as a young man, Priam traveled to Phrygia when Otreus and Mygdon began a campaign towards the Sangarius River and decided to accompany them. It is there, it seems, that they encountered the Amazon forces, whom he decided to fight as an ally of his hosts. He ends his narrative at this point, and we do not know the battle's outcome, although Priam's survival would seem to indicate that it ended in Amazon defeat. Indeed, we know that the cooperation between the two peoples must have grown even closer after these events, for the Phrygians were among the Trojans' allies against the Achaeans.¹⁵

We have already mentioned the existence of several iconographic scenes depicting the agreement between the sovereign and the Amazon queen to take part in this contest,¹⁶ but, as with the rise of the Sauromatian people, the episode on the island of Leuce or the meeting between Alexander and Thalestris, we do not know of a single piece dedicated to this confrontation. Not surprisingly, two coins from Apamea¹⁷ and Ancyra,¹⁸ which followed the Roman trend of depicting the city in the Amazon style, can hardly be associated with the Phrygian kingdom, so much so that they seem to have forgotten

14 Str. 12.24.

15 Hom., *Il.* 2.858; Ps.-Apollod., *Epit.*, 3.3; Str. 12.4.

16 Megarian terracotta cup (175–50 BC, Staatl Mus. 3171); Etruscan relief from Volterra (1st century BC, Museo Guarnacci 429) and several Roman sarcophagi (170 AD, Rome, Galleria Borghese, Saal II, Standortnummer LXXX; Rome, Villa Borghese, LIMC, *Priamos* 76; 170 AD, Palermo, Mus. Naz.).

17 Trebonianus Gallus (251–253 AD, Apameia, Phrygia).

18 Antoninus Pius (138 AD, ANS 1973.191.151).

the ancient disputes mentioned by Homer, apart from alluding to them. The same is true of the few other Amazon pieces linked to Phrygia, a Roman sarcophagus decorated with a relief of the Heracleian Amazonomachy¹⁹ and one of the figures that decorated the Hadrianeum, representing the Asian provinces under Roman control, in this case, dedicated to Phrygia with an Amazon appearance.²⁰ The Asiatic warriors were known for sowing terror among the Anatolian kingdoms with their raids in search of booty, wealth, and territory, whose victories contributed to their fame in antiquity.²¹ Perhaps this explains their presence in Phrygia and why their rulers decided to fight them to end such actions.

Otreus was one of the sons of the Phrygian king Dimas²² and, therefore, the brother of Hecuba, who was to become Priam's wife.²³ This adventure sealed the friendship between the two leaders, to the point of winning the hand of this princess as a reward for her collaboration against the Amazons. Not surprisingly, one of her other brothers, Asius, went on to fight against the Achaeans in the Trojan War.²⁴ Homer mentions the river Sangarius (now the Sakarya, which flows into southern Pontus), which, as a river god, was made the father of Eunoe, wife of Dimante, and mother of Otreus.²⁵ We know of Phrygian pieces depicting the hero Otreus at the time of Geta (193–209 AD), in which he appears on the reverse side,²⁶ although we do not have any works dedicated to this story. Nor does it seem that the Phrygians resisted when the Libyan Amazons crossed their territory,²⁷ as was the case with the Asiatic Amazons.

On the other hand, Mygdon was a descendant of Poseidon and the nymph Melia, king of the Bebryces, a Thracian people who settled in northern Bithynia²⁸. We know that near Lake Ascenius, on the eastern

19 160–190 AD (Phrygia).

20 145 AD (Hadrianeum, a temple of the deified Hadrian in the Campus Martius, Naples National Archaeological Museum 16275378996).

21 Iust., *Epit.* 2.15; Ps.-Callisth. 3.26; Lys. 2.4–6; Str. 9.5, 3; D. S. 2.45.

22 Otreus sometimes appears in the sources as the son of the Dorian king Aegimius (Pin., *P.* 5; Ps.-Apollod., *Epit.* 7.7, 8. 3) and sometimes as a descendant of Phoenix, son of Agenor (Dictys 1.9).

23 Hyg., *Fab.* 91.1; Ps.-Apollod., *Epit.* 3.12, 5; Q. S. 7.606.

24 Hom., *Il.* 17.583–85.

25 Pherecydes of Leros in Scholium to *Iliad* 16.718.

26 Franke, *Kleinasien*, 154; Weber, *Weber Collection*, 7160–61.

27 D. S. 3.40.

28 Ps.-Apollod., *Epit.* 5.9.

border of Bithynia, there was a city called Otroia,²⁹ named after his companion with whom he confronted the Amazons, a name that closely resembles that of the Amazon queen Otrere.³⁰ Arraino also points out that the term “Amazonio” was used to designate different places in Attica, Boeotia, and Bithynia,³¹ which could allude to lost traditions that, in the case of Bithynia, could be related to the customary foundations. His son, Corebo, also participated in the Trojan War because of his love for Cassandra.³²

The Bebryces are already mentioned in the account of Alexander III and his encounter with Thalestris as the cause of the meeting between Candaules, son of Queen Candice, and Alexander III, as the cause of the defeat that forced him to seek refuge in the Macedonian camp.³³ On the other hand, Thracians and Euboeans are mentioned among the allies of the Gargarians against the Amazons,³⁴ so it would not be the only time that the two peoples met. Indeed, the Thracians appear again, in coalition with the Scythians, as responsible for the final defeat that would end the adventure of the Libyan Amazons in Asia Minor, led by Mopso and Sippilus.³⁵ However, when Menecrates of Janto wrote his account of the Bithynian city of Nicaea, he did not mention any of these accounts, but only the myth of Antiope.³⁶

The iconographic records attributed to Bithynia and related to the mythical world of the Amazons are also scarce. In this case, we know of two coins minted in Nicaea³⁷ and Heraclea in Pontus,³⁸ which show only the ninth labor on the reverse, together with a stele decorated with the relief of an Amazonomachy (2nd century AD).³⁹ Not surprisingly, there is evidence that Herakles himself killed Mopso after seizing Hippolyta's belt.⁴⁰

29 Str. 12.4, 7.

30 A. R. 378–390; Hyg., *Fáb.* 30.112 and 163; Tz., *PH.* 8; Ps.-Apollod., *Epit.* 5.1.

31 Arr., *An.* 3.595. 59.

32 Verg., *Aen.* 2.341 ss.

33 Ps.-Callisth. 3.19. Herakles defeated the Bebryces at the time when he faced the Amazons. (Str. 7.3.2; Ps.-Apollod. 2.5.9).

34 Str. 11.5.1–3.

35 D. S. 3.40.

36 Plu., *Thes.* 26–27.

37 Nicaea with Maximinus the Thracian on the obverse (235–238 AD, Bithynia).

38 Heraclea of Pontus under Septimius Severus (193–213 AD, LIMC *Amazons*, 159), Macrinus (217–18 AD, LIMC *Amazons* 161) and Gordian III (238–44 AD, LIMC *Amazons*, 161a).

39 Bursa Archaeological Museum.

40 Tz. ad Lyc. 980.

Phrygia and Bithynia were borderlands, which in turn may have been on the borders of the Amazon kingdom, with the river Sangarius acting as a natural boundary between them,⁴¹ although this situation would imply war rather than defense against a group of Amazons in search of booty. We do not know the earlier situation that Homer did not mention, but we assume they were already organized and established as a people in one of these regions, perhaps in the traditional Thermodon. However, the mouth of the Sangarius is about 700 km from the Amazon, which is perhaps too far away for the Amazons to have extended the borders of their kingdom there. Priam's encounter with them does not surprise him, so Homer makes him aware of their existence. The same must have been true of his audience, for at no point in his work does he stop to explain who these warriors were.⁴² Like any worthy Greek hero, he seems to have managed to defeat them and their allies, which puts them on a par with the most important figures in Greek mythology and thus reinforces their lineage.⁴³

More than seven centuries separate Homer from Strabo (1st century BC – 1st century AD), who will mention this episode even more briefly and with a very different intention.⁴⁴ Undoubtedly, the poet's fame made his work immortal even in antiquity, and he may have become Strabo's source, but he was probably not the only one to remember this episode, although we do not know of its presence in other authors. He devotes the passage to giving his opinion on the veracity of the participation of various peoples in the Trojan conflict as allies of King Priam, according to different traditions. It consists of two distinct parts, the first of which refers to this episode, stating that the Amazons were enemies of the Trojans long before their famous contest with the Achaeans, and they were not the only ones since he also mentions other peoples, such as the Cimmerians and the Trepes.

Apparently, Priam declared war on the Amazons in his youth as an ally of the Phrygians (for nothing is said here, as in Homer, about the Bithynians), so he does not seem to doubt the words attributed to the poet. However, he uses this statement to justify the second part of the commentary, in which he denies any credibility to the presence of

41 Zografou (*Amazons*, 24, 33) states that this incursion would necessarily have also threatened the Hittite fortress of Salappa in the area, occurring shortly before or after the death of Laomedon. Blok, *Early*, 148, indicates that this confrontation would have taken place two generations before the Trojan War.

42 Koromila, *Greeks*, 191.

43 Sanchez Sanz, *Heráldica*, 81.

44 Str. 12.24.

Penthesilea after these events since he does not see how this change in Priam's attitude can be explained nor how they could forget the previous events so close in time. Perhaps Homer thought the same since he never mentions Penthesilea, but we have already remarked how many other authors have tried to resolve this contradiction by attributing to the Amazon queen the need for atonement for the death of her companion.

The Treres and the Cimmerians were historical peoples, quite the opposite of the Amazons, but their joint mention seems to be an attempt to provide further veracity to their existence. There are several references to the Treres in historiography. They are a tribe of Thracian origin, usually associated with the Cimmerians themselves,⁴⁵ who are said to have ravaged Ionia and other regions of Asia Minor from the north,⁴⁶ perhaps in the same way as seems to have happened in Phrygia. Plutarch places the Treres and Tilatheans between Mount Scomburus (or Escomius, the modern Vitosha massif outside Sofia in Bulgaria)⁴⁷ and the river Ostium (modern Iskar, a tributary of the Danube in Bulgaria). The incursions of the Treres and Cimmerian tribes into these regions were well known and almost legendary in the sources, which Strabo uses to justify the Amazon expedition into Phrygia, stating that there was no reason to deny that these peoples had done the same from areas as far away as Thrace or northern Pontus.

Herodotus places the territory of the Cimmerians between the Boristhenes and the Tanais⁴⁸ rivers, driven out by the Scythians around the 7th century BC. We do not know the exact extent of their territory since only the present-day Crimean Peninsula is mentioned with certainty, although it could have been much more extensive, from the mouth of the Danube or the course of the Dniester (where the royal Cimmerian necropolis could be located)⁴⁹ to the Don or the north-western Caucasus. The identification of the Cimmerians has always been difficult, to the extent that their existence has been questioned by the possibility that the sources used the term to refer to the Scythians themselves. We cannot even be sure whether they were a single people or a confederation of different tribes because

45 Th. 2.96; Str. 1.3.18; Stephen of Byzantium 97.16–21.

46 Plu., *Alex.* 1.

47 Th. 2.96.

48 Hdt. 1.6, 15, 103, 4.12. A place in which Homer (*Od.* 11.14) and Aristotle (quoted by Stephen of Byzantium 97.16–21) would locate the cities in which they claim to have lived.

49 Lebedynsky, *Cimmériens*, 95.

of the scarcity of archaeological remains that can be attributed to them⁵⁰ and the fact that they were widely dispersed. In addition, we have only brief mentions in written sources,⁵¹ as well as fragments in Assyrian-Babylonian texts (the *Gimri*)⁵² and passages of the Bible.⁵³ They have even been related to the Camarites, who lived on the east coast of Pontus,⁵⁴ or to the Cimmerians, who are thought to have lived around the Cimmerian Bosphorus,⁵⁵ because of the similarity of the names and despite the distance between this Germanic people and the original Cimmerian homeland.

In any case, apart from the eponymous allusions, the archaeological record has not contributed to the veracity of the account of their expulsion by the Scythians.⁵⁶ Posidonius even points out that the Cimmerian Bosphorus does not owe its name to these people but to the arrival of the Cimbri from the West, who would have been known to the Greeks as the Cimmerians,⁵⁷ something improbable and which

50 Ghirshman, *Manuscrit*, 55 (sheet III, 2, 3, 5–6; IV, 3; VI, 1, 2, 3, 7).

51 Ar., *Lys.* 45; Paus. 10.9,9; Hom., *Od.* 11.14–19.

52 Although Diakonoff, *Cimmerians*, 114–15, argues that this term would be used to define the Scythians or Sakas.

53 Sometimes they are called Gomer or Gamadiens (Gen. 10.2–3; Ez. 38,6 and 27,11).

54 Tac., *Ann.* 3.47; Amm. Marc. 22.8,24; Str. 11.2.12.

55 Plin., *NH.* 6.6; Call., *H.* 253–258; Str. 7.2.2. D. S. 5.32.4.

56 Sauter, *Studiem*, 142, denies this episode, stating that there is no historical evidence of such a confrontation, not even of its consequences in the form of numerous kurgans that would have had to be erected to house the Cimmerians who had fallen in battle. In fact, Ivantchik (*Sinope*, 66) and Ustinova (*Supreme*, 13) do not even grant the Cimmerians their own entity, including them within the material horizon known as “Archaic Scythian,” on the assumption that their socio-cultural and economic characteristics are linked to the nomadic groups of Eurasia.

57 Poseid. (cf. Strab. 7.2,2); Strb. 7.2.2. Pisani (*Griechische*, 37) argues for this. It is possible that when the Romans became acquainted with the climatic conditions of the Jutland peninsula (which was made the homeland of the Cimmerians), its thick fogs, etc. they soon assimilated to the environment in which Homer described the Cimmerians’ home place north of Pontus (Sauter, *Studien*, 178). Hennig, *Neue*, 292, and *Westlichen*, 5, as well as Duncan, *Bede*, 4, already suggested that this climatic panorama was very similar to that of the British Isles, making the Cimmerians and Scythians coincide with Celtic groups located in south-west Britain such as the Scots (also because of the similarity of their names) and the Picts, based on the account of Bede the Venerable (*Historia Ecclesiastica* 1.1), an option which, like Merrills, *History*, 284, we believe to be an invention of our own. Also in Italy, the allusion to the entrance to Hades that is associated with the Cimmerian homeland is used by Pliny to place the Cim-

seems born of a search for an explanation based on the similarity of their names. Plutarch also makes the Cimmerians a tribe belonging to the Celto-Scythian groups that arose in the areas of contact between the two north of Pontus,⁵⁸ although this presupposes a frontier that hardly ever existed.

It has been suggested that the Cimmerians may have been an Iranian tribe who arrived in northern Pontus and the Crimea in the 8th century BC, also from Central Asia,⁵⁹ more specifically modern Kazakhstan,⁶⁰ as their dress, weapons, and customs were very similar to those of the Scythians, Sarmatians or Sakas.⁶¹ However, they may also have been descended from the Srubna (or Wooden Tomb) culture,⁶² which settled between the Dnieper and the Volga in the 16th-10th centuries BC, and the latter from the Yamnaya and earlier Catacomb culture,⁶³ as well as the Sabatinovka culture, which settled between the Danube and the Dnieper in the late Bronze Age.⁶⁴ The rest of their heritage was a mixture of contributions from the Kamychevakh-Tchornohorivka and Novotcherkassk cultures of the northern Caucasus, as well as elements from Siberia and Central Asia, which would have been the most important since two of the three names of Cimmerian rulers recorded in the sources have an Iranian semantic root.

Assyrian documents place the arrival of the Scythians at the end of the 8th century BC,⁶⁵ and they were first mentioned in 681 BC⁶⁶ during their migration across the Caucasus. They briefly settled south of this mountain range,⁶⁷ where they clashed with the Urartians and Assyrians, before moving south of Pontus and reaching the Milesian

rians in the settlement of Cumae, by Lake Avernus (Plin., *NH* 61). The Scots were described by Isidore of Seville, *Orig.* 9.2,103, cf. 14.23,7, as being fond of tattoos, as were the Scythians.

58 Plu., *Mar.* 11.6–8.

59 Lebedynsky, *L'épée*, 20; Prusek, *Chinese*, 119.

60 Harmatta, *Studies*, 37.

61 Sanchez Sanz, *Scythian*, 22.

62 Just like the Scythians; Diakonoff, *Cimmerians*, 123.

63 Mongait, *Archaeology*, 155.

64 Lebedynsky, *Cimmériens*, 70.

65 Waterman, *Royal*, 75–77; Latyshev, *Izvestiya*, 262–69.

66 Some authors use it to indicate the possibility that Cimmerians and Scythians are names of the same group, although not necessarily, as it is possible for a source to mention contemporary groups at similar times and places for a variety of reasons; Latyshev, *Izvestiya*, 270–71; Porada, *Art*, 123.

67 North, north-west or north-east of Urartu; Kristensen, *Who*, 13–14; although Salvini, *Geschichte*, 87, takes them further to the Iranian plateau.

colony of Sinope.⁶⁸ Sources sometimes mention that they made this raid in cooperation with the Amazons⁶⁹ and at a much earlier date (c. 786–783 BC), perhaps on the understanding that there was some feud between the colonists and the nearby Amazon kingdom of Thermodon.⁷⁰ However, the name Sinope has sometimes been associated with the Amazons, although Pseudo-Scymnus recalls that the area then belonged to the Syroi people.⁷¹ The Cimmerians had occupied an earlier city of this people,⁷² only to abandon it shortly afterward and have it rebuilt by the Milesian settlers.⁷³

Their journey continued southwards, attacking Phrygia,⁷⁴ perhaps in the first quarter of the 7th century BC,⁷⁵ and later Paphlagonia, Bithynia, Lydia, and Ionia, destroying important cities such as Sardis⁷⁶ and Ephesus⁷⁷ before disappearing. The Phrygians possibly joined forces with the Urartians to drive them out of the region, so they began to move westwards again,⁷⁸ eventually occupying Phrygia itself.⁷⁹

68 Hdt. 4.12.

69 Even classical sources associate the Amazons with the foundation of Sinope, a city that we know was conquered by the Cimmerians on their journey in Asia Minor, sometimes together with the Thracians; Hdt. 4.12; Ps.-Scymn. 5.948; Hecat., *FHG*. 352.

70 Oros., *Hist.* 1.21.1–2.

71 Ps.-Scymn. 986–97, Diller = F 27 Marcotte = Anon. *Peripl. Pont. Eux.* 22. 8v35–38. This we cannot consider as a periegesis; Rostovtzeff, *Skythien*, 27. Naturally, all the names of Amazons that we know, including those indicated in the sources and those that appear in iconography, show a clear Greek origin, associated with the creators of their mythical universe, or feminized variants of the names of the Scythian kings (such as Scyleia of king Esciles, Bothmer, *Amazons*, 9.39; Beazley Archive 300727).

72 Herodotus 4.12 mentions that they stayed there for a long time, but the archaeological record disproves this. Ivantchik, *Sinope*, 66.

73 As we can see in a fragment of Phlegon of Trales recorded by Stephen of Byzantium; *FGrHist* 257 F 30.

74 Str. 1.3.21.

75 Lebedynsky, *Cimmériens*, 17.

76 Hdt. 1.15.

77 Call., *H.* 251–58.

78 Diakonoff, *Cimmerians*, 109.

79 Dozens of Scythian arrowheads, also used by the Cimmerians, have been found in the walls of the Urartian fortress of Ayanis Kaie, near the Urartian capital and dated to the third quarter of the 7th century BC; Burney, *First*, 79; Ivantchik, *Archäologischen*, 331. However, arrowheads may have served as a bargaining chip used by the Scythians, Thracians and Olbites; Encinas Moral, *Etnogénesis*, 362–63; Grakow, *Skythen*, 30.

We cannot be sure that this is how events unfolded, for it seems difficult to place the Phrygians as allies of the Urartians, notably if the problem could be shifted to their territory, as it seems to have been. Indeed, the Scythians and Cimmerians conceivably acted as Urartian allies against the Assyrians.⁸⁰ Arrian related the Cimmerians and Scythians to each other.⁸¹ If the Cimmerians had never reached the South Caucasus, it would be difficult for them to have ever been known and mentioned by the Assyrians,⁸² as they were located near the kingdom of Urartu (Armenia). Strabo states that the Tretes would have occupied Sardis sometime after the Cimmerians but before the Lycians.⁸³

The last known reference is to their defeat by the Lycian king Aliates, who expelled them from Asia Minor in the 6th century BC, although Arrian places their disappearance in Bithynia, perhaps when they reached that region from Phrygia.⁸⁴ In any case, he states that their enemies were Thracians, so we cannot rule out the possibility that a group of Thracians, possibly the Thracians, met them on a plundering campaign on the other side of the Bosphorus, defeated them, and then conquered Sardis, a sequence of events that fits in with the order of the peoples who attacked the city at the time given by Strabo, and which would explain their relationship with the Cimmerians in the sources.

Some people have tried to identify the Cimmerian women as the origin of the Amazon myth, claiming that they must have taken an active part in the military campaigns because of the supposed parity of the female element in the nomadic societies of antiquity.⁸⁵ This theory is based on the presence of the Cimmerians in Sinope and

80 Azarpay, Urartian, 61; Piotrovskiy, *Vanskoye*, 112–14. We know that in many male and female burials associated with the Urartians and dated to the 8th century BC, a specific type of weapon has been found in the form of a curved-bladed iron knife. This could reflect certain similarities with Scythian and Sarmatian female tombs as evidence of this alliance; Mohen, *Avant*, 207; Sanchez Sanz, *First*, 197–98.

81 In his *History of Bithynia*; Eustath. ad Hom. *Od.* 13.14sq. 1631.27.

82 The oldest Cimmerian material remains have been found in this region. According to Harmatta, *Studies*, 36, part of the Cimmerian people would have migrated to northern Pontus in the 8th century BC, making them the first Iranian nomads to reach western Eurasia.

83 Str. 13.4.8. However, some claim that Strabo is wrong to confuse the two peoples; Diakonoff, *Cimmerians*, 104.

84 Eustath. ad Hom. *Od.* 13.14sq. 1631.27.

85 Ghirshman, *Manuscrit*, 12.

Herodotus' assertion that it was an Amazon foundation,⁸⁶ considering both peoples as one. He claims that the Amazons spoke the Scythian language, which he assumes to be the same as that of the Cimmerians, although forgetting Herodotus' account of the difficulties the Amazons had in communicating with the Scythians themselves.⁸⁷

μετὰ δὲ συμιξαντες τὰ στρατόπεδα οἴκεον ὁμοῦ, γυναῖκα ἔχων
ἕκαστος ταύτην τῇ τὸ πρῶτον συνεμίχθη. τὴν δὲ φωνὴν τὴν μὲν
τῶν γυναικῶν οἱ ἄνδρες οὐκ ἐδυνάετο μαθεῖν, τὴν δὲ τῶν ἀνδρῶν
αἱ γυναῖκες συνέλαβον.

Presently they joined their camps and lived together, each man having for his wife the woman with whom he had had intercourse at first. Now the men could not learn the women's language, but the women mastered the speech of the men.

Hdt. 4.114 (translation by A. D. Godley)

At the same time, he will recall this passage to claim that the Sauromatians fought with their men as part of their Amazon traditions, as did the Cimmerians.

Themyscira would, therefore, have been the capital of the Amazons and the Cimmerian metropolis from which they founded Sinope and used it as a base for their incursions into Asia Minor (although there is no archaeological evidence for this city). Indeed, for supporters of this theory, Homer's passage about the confrontation between Priam and the Amazons would be irrefutable proof that the Cimmerians were already in Asia Minor in the last third of the 2nd millennium BC. However, Strabo acknowledges that the Phrygian kingdom would have been formed between 1000 and 800 BC, which makes a Cimmerian presence in the country even more difficult and further complicates belief in this hypothesis. Not surprisingly, the Amazon accounts were written before Homer's time, when the Cimmerians were campaigning in Asia Minor.

86 Hdt. 4.12.

87 Hdt. 4.114. However, Ivantchik, *Légende*, 213, points to several very different Scythian dialects, which could favor this misunderstanding between Scythian groups, although perhaps never completely.

Fig. 1. Terracotta cup depicting Penthesilea and Priam, from Megara (175-150 BC, Berlin. Staatl. Mus. 3171).

ARCHAEOLOGY SOURCES

With regard to iconography, only one piece of pottery shows a clear link with the Cimmerians. This is the so-called François vase (570–560 BC),⁸⁸ which depicts the Calidonian wild boar hunt, in which one of the hunters with a bow is called *Kimepioe*. It seems clear that here, the name attributed to the culture was used as an anthroponym, similar to another of the archers called Toxamis, a name known in the Amazonian world,⁸⁹ so that the author could also indirectly show this link between the Cimmerians and the Amazons long before Herodotus.

Regarding actual Cimmerian archaeological material, only a few scattered Kurgan burials have been found, perhaps because many of their remains have been misidentified as Scythian or Sakas.⁹⁰ The weaponry includes bows (similar to those of the Scythians),⁹¹ and only one female grave has been found with an awl and an iron needle among the grave goods (Tomb 2 of the Kurgan of Tchornohorivka).⁹² We cannot, therefore, be sure that the female status of the Cimmerians reached the same level as that which we seem to associate with their Scythian, Sarmatian, or Sakas counterparts.

CONCLUSION

Undoubtedly, in the Hellenic collective imaginary, there was a high degree of association between the Amazon cultural sphere and that of many of these cultures, usually associated with a common Iranian origin and a specific geographical context, the Eurasian steppe, which favored not only relations between them but also the transmission of traditions and customs associated with their way of life. Scythians, Thracians, Cimmerians, and Sauromatians appear frequently in their accounts, showing either a direct and causal relationship with the emergence of Amazon society or a circumstantial one that the

88 Archaeological Museum of Florence no. 4209.

89 Two Attic vases show inscriptions alluding to the name of the Amazons they represent: Toxis and Toxaris (Bothmer, *Amazons*, lam. ix. 5, and 7). Curiously, this second option would be used by Lucian of Samosata in the 2nd century AD to title one of his dialogues Toxaris which, precisely, he turns into a plea for sincere friendship (Lizcano, *Tóxaris*, 231) between the Greek Mnesippus and a Scythian who takes that nickname.

90 Diakonoff, *Cimmerians*, 133.

91 Harmatta, *Studies*, 37.

92 Lebedynsky, *Cimmériens*, 78.

authors could easily explain due to geographical proximity or the cultural similarities they established between them. In these accounts, the mythical past is interwoven with actual events that lend credibility to the story, even if they often present contradictions and chronological problems.

The mention of the Teres, Cimmerians, Phrygians, and Trojans placed the Amazons on the same plane of reality regarding the collective imaginary, in which certain events tried to relate to each other to articulate an accepted narrative. However, this is not always the case, or we do not have the necessary information to understand it properly since the initial enmity between Priam and the Amazons makes it challenging to accept that they could later become allies without further explanation, as Strabo himself states. In any case, the purpose of the Amazons' presence in such episodes does not change, as it maintains the didactic character that seems to be at the origin of these stories,⁹³ showing them as mythical figures⁹⁴ of prestige that helped to grant merit and prestige to other characters, but always finally defeated as part of their destiny, understood as logical.

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93 Sanchez Sanz, *Aproximación*, 36.

94 Sanchez Sanz, *Heráldica*, 65.

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ABSTRACT

The legend of the battle of Troy between the hero Achilles and the Amazon queen Penthesilea is one of the most famous stories in Greek mythology. However, we may wonder why the Amazons decided to travel to Troy and become allies of King Priam to fight the Achaeans. This fact is important, especially since this episode does not appear in Homer's work, but the author does mention the Amazons on three occasions. In one of them, King Priam himself is the protagonist, in his youth. Many years before the Achaeans besieged his city, the young Priam traveled to Phrygia, where he decided to accompany the rulers Otreus and Mygdon on their campaign towards the river Sangarius. There, they were surprised by a group of Amazons who did not hesitate to attack them – for no apparent reason. This paper analyzes both episodes' written and archaeological sources to explain why the Amazons decided to change their minds and become Priam's allies after having fought against the Trojan ruler years before. It analyzes the motives of Queen Penthesilea to confront the Achaeans, which would result in her death at the hands of the hero Achilles, who was in love with her.

KEYWORDS: Priam, Penthesilea, Amazons, Achilles, Troy

Uniči sovražnika, ki postaja prijatelj: Priam in Amazonke
v vojni za Trojo

IZVLEČEK

Legenda o bitki za Trojo med junakom Ahilom in amazonsko kraljico Pentezilejo je ena najbolj znanih zgodb grške mitologije. Morda se lahko porodi vprašanje, zakaj so se Amazonke odločile odpotovati v Trojo in postati zaveznice kralja Priama v boju proti Ahajcem. Slednje je še posebej pomembno, ker se ta epizoda v Homerjevih delih ne pojavi. Homer sicer Amazonke omeni trikrat, pri čemer je v eni izmed epizod protagonist sam kralj Priam v svoji mladosti. Daleč preden so Ahajci oblegali Trojo, je mladi Priam odpotoval v Frigijo, kjer se je odločil spremljati vladarja Otreja in Mygdona na njuni vojaški odpravi proti reki Sangarij. Tam jih je presenetila skupina Amazonk in jih – brez očitnega razloga – napadla. Prispevek analizira pisne in arheološke vire obeh epizod ter skuša pojasniti, zakaj so si Amazonke premislile in postale Priamove zaveznice, čeprav so se v preteklosti borile proti trojanskemu vladarju. Obravnava tudi motiv kraljice Pentezileje za spopad z Ahajci; ta se je končal z njeno smrtjo v naročju junaka Ahila, ki je bil zaljubljen vanjo.

KLJUČNE BESEDE: Priam, Pentezileja, Amazonke, Ahil, Troja